

A generalization of the Smarandache function

Hailong Li

Department of Mathematics, Weinan Teacher's College,
Weinan, Shaanxi, 714000, China

Abstract For any positive integer n , we define the function $P(n)$ as the smallest prime p such that $n \mid p!$. That is, $P(n) = \min\{p : n \mid p!, \text{ where } p \text{ be a prime}\}$. This function is a generalization of the famous Smarandache function $S(n)$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the mean value properties of $P(n)$, and give two interesting mean value formulas for it.

Keywords The Smarandache function, generalization, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and results

For any positive integer n , the famous Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. For example, the first few values of $S(n)$ are: $S(1) = 1, S(2) = 2, S(3) = 3, S(4) = 4, S(5) = 5, S(6) = 3, S(7) = 7, S(8) = 4, S(9) = 6, S(10) = 5, S(11) = 11, S(12) = 4, \dots$.

About the elementary properties of $S(n)$, many authors had studied it, and obtained a series results, see references [1], [2], [3], [4] and [5]. In reference [6], Jozsef Sandor introduced another arithmetical function $P(n)$ as follows: $P(n) = \min\{p : n \mid p!, \text{ where } p \text{ be a prime}\}$. That is, $P(n)$ denotes the smallest prime p such that $n \mid p!$. In fact function $P(n)$ is a generalization of the Smarandache function $S(n)$. Its some values are: $P(1) = 2, P(2) = 2, P(3) = 3, P(4) = 5, P(5) = 5, P(6) = 3, P(7) = 7, P(8) = 5, P(9) = 7, P(10) = 5, P(11) = 11, \dots$. It is easy to prove that for each prime p one has $P(p) = p$, and if n is a square-free number, then $P(n) =$ greatest prime divisor of n . If p be a prime, then the following double inequality is true:

$$2p + 1 \leq P(p^2) \leq 3p - 1.$$

For any positive integer n , one has (See Proposition 4 of reference [6])

$$S(n) \leq P(n) \leq 2S(n) - 1. \quad (1)$$

The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the mean value properties of the function $P(n)$, and give two interesting mean value formulas it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusions:

Theorem 1. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} P(n) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot x^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{19}{12}}\right).$$

Theorem 2. For any real number $x > 1$, we also have the mean value formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (P(n) - \bar{P}(n))^2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\bar{P}(n)$ denotes the largest prime divisor of n , and $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

§2. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we shall prove our theorems directly. First we prove Theorem 1. For any real number $x > 1$, we divide all positive integers in the interval $[1, x]$ into two subsets A and B , where A denotes the set of all integers $n \in [1, x]$ such that there exists a prime p with $p|n$ and $p > \sqrt{n}$. And B denotes the set involving all integers $n \in [1, x]$ with $n \notin A$. From the definition and properties of $P(n)$ we have

$$\sum_{n \in A} P(n) = \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p|n, \sqrt{n} < p}} P(n) = \sum_{\substack{pn \leq x \\ n < p}} P(pn) = \sum_{\substack{pn \leq x \\ n < p}} p = \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p. \quad (2)$$

By the Abel's summation formula (See Theorem 4.2 of [7]) and the Prime Theorem (See Theorem 3.2 of [8]):

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are constants and $a_1 = 1$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p &= \frac{x}{n} \cdot \pi\left(\frac{x}{n}\right) - n \cdot \pi(n) - \int_n^{\frac{x}{n}} \pi(y) dy \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2n^2 \ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{b_i \cdot x^2 \cdot \ln^i n}{n^2 \cdot \ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{n^2 \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where we have used the estimate $n \leq \sqrt{x}$, and all b_i are computable constants.

Note that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, and $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln^i n}{n^2}$ is convergent for all $i = 2, 3, \dots, k$. From (2) and (3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in A} P(n) &= \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x^2}{2n^2 \ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{b_i \cdot x^2 \cdot \ln^i n}{n^2 \cdot \ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{n^2 \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right) \right) \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Now we estimate the summation in set B . Note that for any prime p and positive integer α , $S(p^\alpha) \leq \alpha \cdot p$, so from (1) we have

$$\sum_{n \in B} P(n) = \sum_{n \in B} (2S(n) - 1) \leq \sum_{n \leq x} \sqrt{n} \cdot \ln n \ll x^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \ln x. \tag{5}$$

Combining (4) and (5) we may immediately deduce the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} P(n) = \sum_{n \in A} P(n) + \sum_{n \in B} P(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants. This proves Theorem 1.

Now we prove Theorem 2. For any positive integer $n > 1$, let $\bar{P}(n)$ denotes the largest prime divisor of n . We divide all integers in the interval $[1, x]$ into three subsets A, C and D , where A denotes the set of all integers $n \in [1, x]$ such that there exists a prime p with $p|n$ and $p > \sqrt{n}$; C denotes the set of all integers $n = n_1 p^2$ in the interval $[1, x]$ with $n_1 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}$, where p be a prime; And D denotes the set of all integers $n \in [1, x]$ with $n \notin A$ and $n \notin C$. It is clear that if $n \in A$, then $P(n) = \bar{P}(n)$ and $(P(n) - \bar{P}(n))^2 = 0$. So we have the identity

$$\sum_{n \in A} (P(n) - \bar{P}(n))^2 = 0. \tag{6}$$

If $n \in C$, then $P(n) = P(p^2) \geq 2p + 1$. On the other hand, for any real number x large enough, from M.N.Huxley [9] we know that there at least exists a prime in the interval $[x, x + x^{\frac{7}{12}}]$. So we have the estimate

$$2p + 1 \leq P(p^2) \leq 2p + O\left(p^{\frac{7}{12}}\right). \tag{7}$$

From [3] we also have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{n < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} p^2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right). \tag{8}$$

Note that $\bar{P}(n) = p$, if $n = n_1 \cdot p^2 \in C$.

Therefore, from (7) and (8) we have the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in C} (P(n) - \bar{P}(n))^2 &= \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{n < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} (P(np^2) - \bar{P}(np^2))^2 \\ &= \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{n < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} (P(p^2) - p)^2 = \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{n < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} \left(p^2 + O\left(p^{\frac{19}{12}}\right)\right) \\ &= \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{n < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} p^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{31}{24}}\right) \\ &= \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

If $n \in D$ and $(P(n) - \bar{P}(n))^2 \neq 0$, then $P(p^\alpha) \ll S(p^\alpha) \ll p \cdot \ln p$ and $\bar{P}(p^3) \ll p \cdot \ln p$, so we have the trivial estimate

$$\sum_{n \in D} (P(n) - \bar{P}(n))^2 \ll \sum_{3 \leq \alpha \leq \ln x} \sum_{np^\alpha \leq x} p^{\frac{2}{3}} \ll x \cdot \ln x. \quad (10)$$

Combining (6), (9) and (10) we may immediately the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (P(n) - \bar{P}(n))^2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\bar{P}(n)$ denotes the largest prime divisor of n , and $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

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